
Analysis on Linguistic Art of Broadcast Presentation in The Citizen Journalism Era

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ABSTRACT

This study grew out of the fact that effective communication is essential component of broadcast media presentation, as the information and communication technology increasingly grows. Citizen journalism has opportunities and challenges to traditional media. The purpose of this study is to investigate the strategies of language use employed in citizen journalism discourse, and to show traditional broadcast media as professional media whose linguistic art in presentation ought to be improved as to stand the challenges posed by citizen journalism. The paper adopts Norman Fairclough's approach to critical discourse analysis because of its diverse nature and its ability to throw light on different ideologies. Since this analysis is related to the use of language as tool of power it helped in revealing various linguistic art choices analyzed in the discourse. The sources of data in this paper are publications, and health influencer discourse topics from the 'You tube'. The paper adopts a descriptive approach in the analysis of data. Two health influencer topics as primary source of data were transcribed and analyzed with every complete sentence forming a line. The analysis revealed the linguistic art of citizen journalism characterized by conversational tone, fashionable style, inclusive language, personalization, humor and emotive language. The paper concludes that this digital era calls for new language expression in broadcasting, as it calls on traditional media to evolve and embrace the linguistic art of citizen journalism, as to remain relevant, credible and impactful in this digital age.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The new media era increasingly progresses and the use of blogs to promote citizen journalism is a significant phenomenon across the globe. To this effect huge impact is being made on the traditional roles of the traditional media. The possibility to express one's self on internet becomes easier. The use of blogs in citizen journalism began in the mid 90's though was not widely recognized as a journalistic tool by the professionals and institutions until 2000 (Simon 2007, 2008, Flew 2008).

The advent of citizen journalism has refocused the new media by making them a more interactive product. It is time that changes should be made to the presentation mode of the traditional media so as to adapt to the development of the citizen journalism era. The broadcast hosts who are responsible for delivering information to the whole public play a very important role in the whole society. The use of blogs to promote citizen journalism as an emerging trend that cannot be divorced from internet offers users to be a part of gathering and disseminating of news and other programmes.

This paper investigates the strategies of language use of blogs in promoting citizen journalism as the reason for the broadcast media to braze up in their delivering of programmes through their improvement in linguistic art of broadcasting as to showcase professionalism that is lacking in the citizen journalism. The paper begins with brief introduction, followed by theoretical framework. It expounds on the citizen journalism and examines the strategies of language use in citizen journalism adverts, and how they facilitate social change by amplifying underrepresented perspective, and overviews the linguistic art in traditional broadcasting: challenges and solutions in presentation.

1.2 Statement of Problem

The dominance of traditional media outlets has resulted in a lack of diversity in language use, thereby limiting the representation of the marginalized voices. The study investigates the strategies of language use employed in citizen journalism discourse, and how they facilitate social change by amplifying underrepresented perspectives.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

1. To analyze the language strategies used in the health influencer discourse.
2. To identify and interpret underlying social, cultural and ideological values embedded in the health influencer discourse.
3. To explore how the discourse position the viewer or consumer.
4. To examine the health influencer discourse use of persuasive strategy devices.
5. To evaluate the potential impact of linguistic art choices in citizen journalism to the traditional media.

1.4 Research Questions

1. What social cultural or ideological values are embedded in the health influencer discourse?
2. How does the health influencer discourse use power dynamics, such as persuasion or manipulation?
3. What language strategies are used to construct the message?
4. What language strategies are used to promote social change?
5. What are the implications of linguistic art choices of the discourse to traditional media?

1.5 Theoretical Framework

This study adopts Norman Fairclough(1989)'s approach to Critical Discourse Analysis. Fairclough's CDA theory focuses on the relationship between language, power and social change. Fairclough's model is chosen because of its eclectic nature and its ability to throw light on different ideologies. Since this study is related to the use of language as a tool of power, it helps in unearthing various issues that are creatively worded. Its affordance to consider all aspect of language makes it a good approach to this study. It is tagged 'the three –dimensional model' as its methods are grouped into three interrelated aspects, namely, text, process and socio- historic conditions. The text is the object to be considered, which could be verbal or nonverbal, the process is concerned with the production and reception of the text, while the socio-historic aspect deals with the conditions involved in the process. The theory helps to analyze how language forms and shapes various social practices. The theory foregrounds various issues and provides linguistic evidence to ideological orientations discovered.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concept of Citizen Journalism

With the rise of social media, citizen journalism continues to soar as many people are seizing the opportunity to spread news awareness, and other valuable information to public. Blogs also known as web-logs, have become popular in recent years. They are frequently modified web pages in which dated entries are listed in reverse chronological sequence (Herring, Scheidt, Bomis and Wright 2004).

Citizen journalism is that journalism that is conducted by the people who are not professional journalists but who disseminate information using websites blog media. The professional traditional media when writing takes into account the audience, the tone in which the piece is delivered, where accuracy, brevity and clarity is accounted for, this makes the traditional media professional as against citizen journalism. However, citizen journalism has had a great impact on the media industry by challenging traditional gate-keeping roles and bringing attention to underreported issues. In other words, citizen journalism can be seen in the ability to fill the void created by traditional media's neglect of community orientated news and events reporting. Flew (2007)states that there are three elements critical to the rise of citizen journalism and citizen media. These include open publishing, collaborative editing and distributed content.

From the perspective, Wikipedia itself is the Largest and most successful citizen journalism project with news often breaking through Wikipedia editors and stories being maintained as new facts emerge. Wikipedia is a free, web based collaborative, multilingual encyclopedia project supported by the non-profit Wikimedia foundation. The traditional media seem to consider an audience as receivers waiting to be filled with information selected by omniscient editors and those whose only interaction with the media is to buy what is sold or not.

Simons (2008) states that crowd sourcing is the idea that a crowd of people geographically dispersed but sharing common purpose, can achieve things better or differently than small groups of professional gatekeepers. It is the idea behind Wikipedia, but also many other internet enabled ventures use it. The internet allows readers and viewers to directly sample and locate sources of news. Bloggers take up different initiatives to express ideas, irrespective of their educational or professional background. In practice, citizen journalists use blog, Wikis, digital story telling applications, photo and video-sharing sites. In other words citizen journalism is an alternative form of news gathering and reporting functions outside mainstream media, filling the gaps left by mainstream media with similar journalistic practices but is driven by different objectives. The advantages of citizen journalism also include: hyper local coverage and real-time fact checking. It can cover the events that the mainstream media might otherwise miss. News can be gathered without it being controlled or swayed by political parties.

The Weak Points of the Citizen Media:

As many people are seizing the opportunity to spread news, awareness and other valuable information to the public with rise of social media, many people believe that they are spreading news based on the benefit of some and somewhat deviating from truth. A major criticism against citizen journalism is the issue of the people involved in the spreading of the news and events not having professional training. Most people in the traditional media are with professional careers in journalism, broadcast journalism, presentation of programmes training, etc. With good education, the traditional media professionals can avoid plagiarism; know how to report a story and how to report objectively and ethically.

Citizen journalism can be subjective that one's thoughts and beliefs may influence it as more of an opinion rather than a fact. These days the enormous capabilities of storage devices have given photographers, graphic workers and others a new tool level: the ability to manipulate images at the pixel level. Citizen journalism can disclose classified documents. Blogging on the internet has no uniformed rules or regulations. This makes bloggers to post comments without fear or being charged for defamation. At times, people make sarcastic or condemnatory comments on posts which can trigger crises especially when they affect a race, tribe or religion.

2.2 Linguistic art in broadcasting; Challenges and Solutions in Presentation:

The main thrust of modern linguistics has to do with the study of how a message is encoded bearing in mind the channel of communication with possible sources of noise, and with how the message is decoded. Three broad aspects are recognized, namely, meaning, form and substance in linguistics. Meaning has to do with message encoded and transmitted. Breakdown in communication may be due to the receiver as a result of an imperfect knowledge of the code. And finally breakdown may be due to the source nor to the receiver by the noise, or what the linguist calls interference. In such a case, the sender encodes perfectly and he decodes perfectly, but the message has been interfered within transit, so what was decoded is different from what was encoded.

The study of form which is central to the science of linguistics is concerned with how the message is encoded. In natural language the encoding involves structuring at the phonological syntactic and lexical levels. The study of substance deals with the study of the channel. Linguistic substance can either be phonic or orthographic. This means that in natural language a message is transmitted either in speech or in writing. Phonic is primary in the sense that, there is no known living human language which does not use that channel (phonic). The orthographic channel on the other hand, is deviatory in the sense that it is basically the reduction of phonic cues to visual forms. What this simply means is that language is either spoken or written, heard or read, and that the ability to write or read a language depends on a prior ability to speak that language and understand it when it is spoken.

It is clear that the final test of mastery in a language is the ability of the individual to match the use of language with total context of situation so that perfect justice is done simultaneously to the field of discourse, the mode of discourse and the tender of the discourse. This ability is referred to in Linguistics as communicative competence to be distinguished from grammatical competence. This is the competence required of a professional broadcast practitioner, hence the linguistic art of broadcasting improvement to out shine the self-media practitioners of this era.

Linguistic art, what is it? : Carter, R. and McRae, J. (1986, p15)'Linguistic art refers to the use of language in a way which is aesthetically pleasing or which conveys meaning in way which is not straight forwardly referential'

Presentation: Owuamalam, E.O (2006, P.22) States that "presentation is skillful act of introducing a programme to an audience" that artistic conjecturing, which makes programmes palatable for consumption is the art of presentation. In other words effective communication, which embraces all aspect of linguistic art in broadcasting, is presentation with its attendant audience satisfaction. Presentation provides the audience the vital information, required to adjust their listening or viewing desire.

Principles, challenges and solutions to broadcast presentation:

The principles of presentation deal with these issues, which make presenters believable and acceptable to an audience.

Diction: the ability to pronounce words distinctly and clearly determines to large extent how the audience understands the information, which is to be shared with presenter. Presenters allow their information to be machine conveying text with language and voice. Broadcast presenter language should be normative, which requires clear pronunciation, smooth speech with appropriate verbal expression according to different semantic contexts, relative stressing, slow or fast pronunciation, tone, pause phonetic changes etc. Tonal stress must be accurately emphasized at the relevant points, in order to state exactly, what the presenter means. Clarity of meaning is the essence of good diction. The goal of pronunciation training is intelligible pronunciation, which is essential component of communicative competence. Pronunciation stands as an obstacle in communication, especially when the meaning of a certain word or expression is altered as result of wrong pronunciation.

Speaking well means production of beautiful words, in an impressive manner. Good phonetics is the key to mutual understanding between the presenter as an artiste and the audience as consumer. Each language must be spoken according to its phonetic rules. Any deviation may generate channel noise, inimical to the clarification of meaning. The safe media these days present programmes with clannish or parochial interest. Broadest presenters in mainstream media should by their good pronunciation eliminate ethnic biases as they follow the phonetic rules of the language of presentation. Exaggerated speech mannerism in any specific language in order to impress rather than to express a thought or feeling should be avoided. The presenter as a receptionist for broadcast stations' programmes must be presentable and friendly, with his own standpoint attitude express sincere emotions and play role of educating, leading and mobilizing the audience.

Mood and Emotion: the use of body language aids in the articulation of meaning, especially when accompanied by words. Broadcast language without emotion and incitation only make broadcast work indifferent and ordinary without any vitality. Presenters set the mood for the appreciation of any programme in broadcasting, through the manner of its delivery to an audience. Broadcast presenter should always have their true disposition not just the basic requirement of sound pronunciation and full tone in this era of citizen journalism.

It is the onus of the presenter to ensure that the proper mood and emotional feelings are aroused in line with the programme objective. The presenter represents the position and image of the programme, which requires his reasonable and evidence based language expression. What gives the mainstream media edge over the self-media (citizen journalism) is the sincere and plain statement of objective facts and expression of logical ideas rather than flaunty false and empty languages.

Competence: the competence of presenter is acquired through experience and qualification. A presenter should be knowledgeable in the programme to be presented. It is from the knowledge that competence is drawn, to guide audience properly, through a programme. Experience shows how programmes are to be introduced and handled, in order to guarantee audience acceptance.

The presenter is a student and researcher of issues, which have relevance, to the programme to be handled. Audience follows a programme, more faithfully, where an insight into the origin of the matter is identified and highlighted. Back grounding, helps the presenter to put his work in the proper artistic perspective and the template, for interpreting performance. The presentation should not be verbose, but brief, precise and clear, so that the duration used for the purpose, would not take much of the programme time. A major criticism against citizen journalism is issue of processional training. Those with professional careers in journalism generally have journalism education, broadcasting education that put them in check on how to report a story or present programme objectively and ethically.

Charisma: The possession of an impressionable personality bestows dignity and attracts fellowship. Presenter requires special endowment, which endears the talent to the audience. In this self-media era everyone is a presenter with or without the charisma of presentation.

Audience Participation: the attribute which presenters exhibit in order to carry the audience along known as audience participation has to do with their effort at audience engineering. The adoption of concept of mental picturisation using appropriate descriptive words, in explaining details about an event or a subject is presenter's way of luring the audience to the programme. The use of psychological closure communication, allows the audience too to participate in the programme. Good judgment in determining effective strategies for audience participation, guide presenters in the broadcast media. Blogging on the internet has no uniform rules or regulations.

3.0 STUDY METHODOLOGY

The data used in this study were collected from both the primary and secondary sources. The primary source was drawn from the transcription of two health influencer discourse topics from the You Tube. These two health talks from Aporok doctor, showing some linguistic features and developing trend in the citizen journalism era were analyzed. For the secondary source insights were gained from text books. This study adopts a descriptive approach in the analysis of the data.

The two health influencer discourse topics of Egemba Chinoso Fidelis popularly known as Aporoko Doctor born 26 October,1990 a Nigerian doctor and health influencer , titled 'Aporoko Nation Milk Advert' and 'Na who Dey Alive Dey Mess' were transcribed and analyzed with every complete sentence forming a line.

3.1 Data Analysis and Discussion of findings

This section is concerned with the data analysis and discussion of findings of two Aproko doctor's discourse topics from the social media (You Tube Reel) titled 'Aproko Nation Milk Advert' and 'Na who Dey Alive Dey Mess.'

3.2 'Aporoko Nation' Milk Advert(1)

Nkechi, Amaka, Philo, infact all the mothers in the house I have something to tell you {line 1}.

I know that some of you have been wondering what you can give your children so that they can be sharp and active {line 2}.If you asked this question before your answer is here{line3}.Come, let me show you first, children should drink milk, especially Emeka and Junior, because is a rich source of nutrients that is needed for their growth and development{line 4}.

Milk also contains nutrients like potassium and magnesium which is also good for the heart and you already know that milk is an easy way for kids to get the necessary nutrients {line5}.

The next is calcium, calcium is very important for kids to function properly and see, Amaka, I hope you know for their bones and teeth to form properly you need to add food that is rich in calcium too{line 6}. See, eh I know that the last one will shock you, cocoa, yes-o-o, children can consume cocoa in moderation, because it offers health benefits like good source of antioxidants which can protect you from damage {line 7}.It also contains minerals like iron, magnesium and zinc {line 8}. I know that Nkechi is already thinking,' how am I going to give them all these things' {line 9}.But Nkechi can you give Emeka raw cocoa to eat or ask them to be chewing calcium? {line 10}. No, abi! so good, that is why you should feed your child in new and improved Milo, because it already has milk, calcium and even cocoa in it, yes, it's made with six essential vitamins with natural goodness of malt with real milk and fortified with six essential vitamins with three mineral{line 11}. The new and improved Milo now has nutrients that support energy release so that your pikin dem, your children can make the most of their active days {line 12}. So Emeka, Junior, does not have any energy is not concentrating well in school is not your village people, is probably because he has very low energy and needs the nutrient that is packed inside this Milo{line13}. Ndi nne!! MaMa!!, in the house, see this your sign to also make Milo your child's everyday's choice and Aproko Nation also am saying this again make sure that children have

balance diet plus the delicious and nutritious Milo{ line14}.It is not just about great taste is also about providing the adequate nourishment that they need to tackle their day{ line 14}. Enh!! Aporoko why are you drinking Milo?{ line 15}. We are all children of God { line 16}.

Aporoko Health Discourse (2) Na Who Dey Alive Dey Mess :

Anybody that tells you that they don't use to mess is a liar { line17}. Even that your celebrity, that your crush, eh!! Nkechi she use to mess too, including me that is making the video { line18}. As a matter of fact is the sign that your digestive process is healthy {line 19}. I just want you people to open up to me, because when you eat as you are eating and swallowing the food you also swallow air into stomach, that air has to go somewhere, is either is coming out of mouth or is coming in, or coming out of the other place...(mmmh){ line20}.

Number two when you eat some heavy , really heavy food is not all that use to break down, some of them will go down your intestine and then bacteria starts acting on it inside, acting on it creates some gasses{line21}. Is not all mess that smell bad, as a matter of fact some mess contain methane, it use to smell sweet somehow however the one that use to burst everywhere is the one that contains hydrogen sulfide, yes, that is the one they know you for {line22}. As matter of fact your body processes almost two liters of mess per day {line23}. What am I trying to say in this video is that mess is normal {line24}. If your mess is disturbing the function of your life it is time you see a doctor because you may have abdominal problem that you really need to be treated and is probably the kind of food you eat{line25}. Also if beans use to make you mess soak the beans for some hours before you cook it, it can help that your crush that you slept in the night with, during the night they don't use to control how the mess comes out, so before you sleep with somebody find out if you can really like his mess {line26}.Thank you very much {line27}.

3.3 Discussion of findings:

Research question 1: What social cultural ideological values are embedded in the health discourse: The discourse as drawn from "Aporoko Nation and Na who Dey Alive Dey Mess" have answers to this question. In line 1 of the discourse on milk where Aporoko doctor states thus 'Nkechi, Amaka, Philo, in fact all the mothers in the house...' this depicts humor and the impact of cultural connection to the rightful audience, making the discourse more relatable and trustworthy. This is equally giving representation and visibility to the underrepresented. ' Ndinne Mama in the house...' in line 13 has also social and cultural implications, as using local names in a discourse can create a sense of cultural connection and shared identity between the speaker and the audience. Local names in a discourse provides context and helps to situate the discourse within a specific cultural, social, or geographical setting. In lines 11, 12, code -mixing are seen in the discourse. Mixing code adds cultural authenticity to the discourse, making it more relatable and engaging. Social bonding is being created in the discourse through the code-mixing, as audience members are engaged creating sense of familiarity and shared knowledge.

Research question 2: How does the health influencer discourse use power dynamics such as persuasion or manipulation: Reiteration of words and expressions are seen in lines 4, 6, 9,10, 13, 17, 22, 23, 24, 26 of the discourse, which help to stress key points, making the messages impactful. Line 4 has this ... especially Emeka and Junior...,line 6- Amaka I hope you...,line 9- I know Nkechi is already thinking..., line10-But Nkechi can you give Emeka raw cocoa ..., line 13-...so Emeka, Junior does not have energy..., line 17...does not mess is a liar, line22- Is not all mess that smell bad..., line23... almost two liter of mess per day, line 24...mess is normal...,line25—If your mess is disturbing the function...,line 26...control how the mess comes out. These reiterations have conversational impact as in face –to-face communication, and emphatic enough to convey passion and enthusiasm.

Research question3: What language strategies are used to construct the message? Aporoko doctor[Health Influencer] used conversational strategy in the discourse to create a sense of familiarity and shared experience with the audience. The conversational strategy is portrayed in the use of interjections, code switching and personalization and humor, as seen in these lines: Interjections—line 7...eh!! I know..., line 15 Enh! Aporoko why..., line 18...eh!! Nkechi...Code-mixing—line11 No, abi!, line 12...so that your pikin dem, your children them... Personalization-line 15- ...Aporoko why are you drinking Milo, line 16 We are all children of God. Humor- line 20 ...or coming out of the other place... mmmm! This is euphemizing anus, hereby creating humor. Mess is used instead of farting severally in lines 18,22,23,24 and 26. All these created rapport with the audience.

Research question 4: What language strategies are used to promote social change?

Fashionable language style: The discourse has fashionable language style that adds creativity and originality to the discourse. Line 18 of the discourse attest to this with this expression; 'Even that your that your celebrity, that your 'crush' eh!! Nkechi she use to mess too... The term 'crush' has evolved in its usage, especially among younger generations as strong admiration word for someone's boy or girl friend. Fashionable language can create emotional resonance with the audience, evoking feeling and excitement. The discourse is made memorable and catchy with fashionable language style.

Conversational tone: The discourse employed conversational tone that mimics face to face communication, establishing rapport; as in these lines of the discourse. Line 2—I know that some of you have been wondering..., line 4—Come, let me show you first...,line 20—I just want you people to open up to me..., line 24—What am I trying to say in this video is that mess is normal.

Inclusive language: The health influencer employed inclusive language, using 'they' instead of 'he' or 'she' as in lines 17 and 26. Line 17- 'Anybody that tells you that 'they' don't mess is liar.'Line26-...that your 'crush' that you slept in the night with, during the night 'they' don't use to control how the mess comes out... Using inclusive language promotes diversity, equity, and inclusion.

Emotive language: Emotive language is to engage audience and convey emotion; as in line 7- 'I know that the last one will shock you, cocoa, yes-o-o, children can consume cocoa in moderation.'

Humor: Humor is used to relax the atmosphere making the audience more receptive to the message; as used in lines 10 and 22 of this study. Line 10- 'But Nkechi can you give Emeka raw cocoa to eat or ask them to be chewing calcium? Line 22— 'Some mess

contain methane, it use to smell sweet somehow, however the one that use to burst everywhere is the one that contains hydrogen sulfide, yes that is the one they know you for.

Research question 5: What are the implications of linguistic art choices of the discourse to traditional media? The linguistic of Citizen Journalism, as evident in this analysis, has revolutionized the way we consume and interact with broadcast presentations. The conversational tone, fashionable style, inclusive language, personalization, humor, and emotive language employed by the citizen journalists have created a distinctive narrative voice that resonates with diverse audience members. In contrast, traditional media often struggles to connect with younger generations and marginalized communities. The rigid, formal tone and outdated language used by traditional media can come across as detached and elitist. Therefore, it is imperative that traditional media outlets take a cue from citizen journalism and adapt to the changing media landscape. By incorporating conversational tone, fashionable style, and inclusive language, traditional media can increase engagement, build trust, and foster a more inclusive public discourse. Moreover, embracing the linguistic art of citizen journalism can enable traditional media to reclaim its role as a facilitator of democratic participation and social change. By doing so, traditional media can stay relevant, credible, and impactful in the digital age.

CONCLUSION

Ultimately, this analysis highlights the significance of linguistic art in citizen journalism demonstrating how linguistic art choices, characterized by conversational tone, fashionable style, inclusive language, personalization, humor and emotive language can shape public discourse, influence social attitudes and foster a more inclusive and participatory broadcasting. The linguistic art of citizen journalism as evident in this analysis has revolutionized the way we consume and interact with broadcast; meaning broadcasting in this digital age requires new language expression to be impactful to the audience. To this effect traditional media should cue into this trend to remain relevant.

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